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OIL REVENUE AND INCOME INEQUALITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examines the effect of oil revenue on income inequality in Nigeria using a time series data from 1990 to 2014. The Error Correction Model (ECM) was employed on the time series data in order to study the effect of oil revenue on income inequality in Nigeria. The study adopted a country-specific approach using oil revenue, Gini coefficient and macroeconomic data from 1990-2014. Data were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Statistical Bulletin, Index Mundi, World Bank Indicators and relevant literatures. From the empirical result, a negative and robust relationship was found to exist between inflation rate (INFL) and income inequality in Nigeria with t -statistic value of (-1.818855). A negative, but statistically insignificant relationship was also found to exist between oil revenue (OIL REV), government recurrent expenditure on social and community services (GREXP) and income inequality with t -statistic values of (-0.252134) and (-0.058335) respectively. While RealGDP had a positive statistically significant relationship with income inequality having a reported a t -statistic value of (2.198320). It was concluded that though oil revenue reduces income inequality, the high level corruption in the oil industry has made it non-realistic due to the continuous increase in the gap between the poor and the rich in the economy. Thus, it was recommended among others, that the government should put necessary measures in place in order to checkmate the high level of corruption in the oil industry and the nation at large.

KEYWORDS: Oil revenue, Income inequality, Gini coefficient, Error Correction Model.

JEL CLASSIFICATION: Q32, O15, D31, C32.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Variation in income is highly visible in most part of the economies of developing nations, Nigeria inclusive. The income and wealth of the nation seem to be unevenly distributed (Bakare, 2012). Income inequality may be considered in relation to a number of factors such as occupation, religion, education, ethnicity, government expenditure pattern, tax system/policies,

abundance of natural resources (e.g. Crude oil) etc., but the extent to which the revenue generated from the latter (crude oil) affects income distribution has been a subject of protracted debate in the natural resource-rich third world nations, though with less emphasis in Nigeria.

Inequality refers to the gap between the rich and the poor. According to the OECD (2011), income inequality has always existed, but the growing concern is due to the increasing gap between the rich and the poor globally. Nigeria's income inequality is more or less as a result of the country's over dependence on oil. In Nigeria, oil accounts for about 90-95 percent of the export revenue, over 90 percent of foreign exchange earnings and about 80 percent of the government's revenue (Jibrin, Blessing & Ifurueze, 2012). And due to Nigeria's dependence on crude oil, there are some indications of income inequality increasing farther with higher levels of oil production (Martin & Crookes, 2013).

This study was motivated by the less emphasis Researchers particularly in Nigeria have given to oil revenue in relation to its impact on income inequality. This study contributed to knowledge by adopting a country-specific approach in determining the impact of oil revenue on income inequality as against the predominant cross-country approach (Mallaye, Yogo, & Timba, 2005; Fum & Hodler, 2009; Leamer, Maul, Rodrigueze & Schoot, 1999; and Buccellato & Alessandrini, 2009). A cross-country approach only presents pooled estimates, but fails to separate the result for each specific unit of study (Ilaboya & Ohonba, 2013).

1.1 Statement of Research Problem

A number of contributions of erudite researchers have enhanced our understanding on income inequality against variables such as literacy, GDP, inflation rate, employment rate, ethnicity, government social expenditure, natural resource abundance, etc. However, very few has related oil revenue to income inequality using cross-country data. It is to this end that this paper therefore seeks to contribute to this research stream by answering the fundamental question: what is the effect of oil revenue on income inequality in Nigeria?

1.2 Research Objectives

The fundamental objective of this study was to examine the effect of oil revenue on income inequality in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. examine the relationship between inflation rate and income inequality in Nigeria;
- ii. investigate the relationship between Real GDP and income inequality in Nigeria; and
- iii. determine the relationship between government recurrent expenditure on social and community service and income inequality in Nigeria.

The paper therefore proceeds as follows: Section 2 presents an overview of relevant literatures beginning with a theoretical framework to empirical review. Section 3 entails the methodology

of the study. Section 4 presents the data analysis and discussion of results. Finally, Section 5 presents the summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations of the study.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Empirical Review

The most commonly used measure of income inequality is the GINI coefficient. It measures the extent to which income (or in some cases, consumption) among the individuals or the households surrounded by an economy deviates from a perfectly equal distribution (Gylfason & Zoega, 2002). The Gini coefficient invented by an Italian Sociologist, Corrado Gini, ranges from 0 to 1. A Gini coefficient of 0 shows that everyone has equal income, while a Gini coefficient of 1 indicates that all income goes to only one person. Thus, the lower the Gini coefficient, the higher the income equality within the economy and vice-versa. However, there seems to be a tendency that the more egalitarian a country is, the smaller the country's Gini coefficient (OECD, 2011). Some erudite Researchers such as (Adegoke, 2013; Awe & Rufus, 2012; Bakare, 2012; Buccellato & Alessandrini, 2009; Fum & Hodler, 2009; Gylfason & Zoega, 2002; Ilaboya & Ohonba, 2013; Mallaye, Yogo & Timba, 2015; Martin & Crookes, 2013; Moradi, 2009; etc.) have applied Gini coefficient as a measure for inequality in their various studies. Income distribution is core to the development of any nation. This simply explains the popularity which issues of income distribution have gained among various Scholars in Economics. In developing nations, income distribution has become a contemporary issue which has enjoyed the patronage of some erudite Researchers such as Bulir (1998), Rossana and Hoeven (2001), Jose and Teilings (2002), Oguntuase (2007), Moradi (2009), Buccellato and Alessandrini (2009), Awe and Rufus (2012), Martin & Crookes (2013), Giovanni (2012), Ilaboya and Ohonba (2013), etc.

Oil revenue and Gini Coefficient

Moradi (2009) analyzing the effects of oil resource abundance on two major macroeconomic variables, economic growth and income distribution in Iran using data over the period 1968-2005, and employing the Error Correction Model, Co-integration test and the ARDL bounds technique, the results of both models confirm that although oil revenue has a positive effect on GDP and negative effect on Gini coefficient, the magnitude of the coefficients in both models were too small. Thus, the effect of oil revenue on economic growth and income distribution was not very strong. Fum and Hodler (2009) in their study hypothesized that natural resources raise income inequality in ethnically polarized societies, but reduce income inequality in ethnically homogeneous societies. Using a Baseline regression, empirical findings supported their hypothesis. Buccellato and Alessandrini (2009) in their empirical study based on an unbalanced

panel of 122 countries over the period 1980-2004 made use of Ores and metals as the variable capturing the effect of natural resources an inequality dynamics. Employing Regression analysis, their results suggested that ores and the metals are seemed to have a clear and significant role in enhancing inequality within countries, and that the economic dependence on exports of ores and metals widens the gap between the two types of households. In more recent studies, Martin and Crookes (2013) using a mix of quantitative and qualitative analysis in their work titled, “oil shock vulnerabilities and impacts: Nigeria case study”, concluded that higher oil prices have positive benefits in terms of government spending and also from the Nigerian government’s ability to subsidize the fuel price, which has benefitted many Nigerians. On the other side of the divide, higher oil prices were seen to have increased inequality and also resulted in higher food prices, which adversely affected inflation and increased poverty.

Inflation Rate and Gini Coefficient

Inflation rate is the rate of general increase of a price index (eg. Consumer Price Index). It can also be referred to as the percentage rate of change in price level over time. Rossana and Hoeven (2001) in their study titled, “Is inflation bad for income inequality?” The researcher used both theoretical as well empirical data to study the impact of monetary policy and inflation on income inequality in developed nations. The data collected from the United State and a sample of 15 OECD countries was analyzed using the OLS regression technique. Their results revealed that in high inflation countries, restrictive monetary policy is often beneficial for income inequality. The empirical study of Bulir (1998) titled, “Income inequality: Does inflation matter?” made contributions to the income inequality literature that was based on traditional Kuznet model. Income inequality (proxy by GINI coefficient) was expressed as a function of the level of development, state employment, fiscal redistribution and price stability. His findings showed that there is a non-linear impact of price stability on income distribution. Thus, concluding that the reduction in inflation from hyper-inflationary levels significantly lowers income inequality, while a further reduction to a very low level of inflation seems to bring about insignificant additional gains in the GINI coefficient of income distribution. Jose and Teilings (as cited in Awe & Fufus, 2012) carried out an empirical study by conducting a research with a view to investigate the causes of the substantial changes in income distribution over time. Their model captured changes in income inequality in transitional countries by a number of explanatory variables. The Gini coefficient of income inequality (GINI) was expressed as a function of adjusted GDP per capital (GDPPC), inflation rate (INFL), employment rate (EMP), government consumption percentage of GDP (CONSG), industrial output as a percentage of GDP (INVA), private sector share of the GDP (PIVS), percentage of old people above 60 years (SH60), government social employment and the error term (U_1). They employed the regression model on 24 transitional countries and their result revealed that per capital GDP and income inequality had a strong negative relationship, which implies that inequality may rise during a period of recession. Inflation was found to increase income inequality, while employment rate and

government consumption failed to have any significant effect on income inequality. Also, government social expenditure was found to lead to fall in income inequality.

RealGDP and Gini Coefficient

Awe and Rufus (2012) expressed income inequality in the Nigerian economy (proxy by Gini coefficient) as a function of a number of explanatory variables such as: employment rate (EMPR), inflation rate (INFR), growth rate of output (GDP), government expenditure on health (HE) and government expenditure on education (EDE). Employing the Co-integration analysis and the Error correction model on the variables for a time series of 1977-2005, the empirical findings in the study has revealed that Gini coefficient is high in Nigeria. It indicates a high level of income inequality. The study further revealed that, both the growth rate of output and government health expenditure exhibited a negative relationship with Gini coefficient, while employment rate, inflation rate and government education expenditure had a positive relationship with Gini coefficient of income distribution in the Nigerian economy. Finally, the study concluded that employment rate, inflation rate, GDP and government social spending are true determinants of income distribution in Nigeria. Giovanni (2012) examined inequality trends and their determinants applying data from Latin America for periods ranging from 1990-2010. Employing the Least Square Dummy Variable (LSDV) model, it was observed that changes in the explanatory variables accounted for 64% variation in the inequality over 2002-2009, while in the GMM, it reduced to 35%. It was further observed in the LSDV model that GDP per capita had a negative, but negligible effect on income inequality. Ilaboya and Ohonba (2013) examined the relationship between direct versus indirect taxation and income inequality in Nigeria using macroeconomics data from 1980-2011. They expressed Gini coefficient as a function of explanatory variables such as: Tax ratio, Total tax revenue (TTR), Tax burden (TBUD) GDP per capita (GDPPC), private sector to GDP ratio (Pcredit/GDP) and labour force participation (LFP). The study employed a combination of Co-integration and Error Correction Model and the results revealed that there exists a negative and robust relationship between total tax revenue, tax burden and income inequality in Nigeria. While a negative, but insignificant relationship was found to exist between GDPPC, Pcredit/GDP, tax ratio * TR and income inequality. The result further showed a positive, but an insignificant relationship between LFP and TDT/TIT with income inequality.

Government Recurrent Expenditure on Social and Community Services and Gini Coefficient

Irish, Martinez-Vazquez and Vulovic (2012) examined government fiscal policies and redistribution of income using data from 1970-2009 for Asian countries. Employing Panel

Estimation in the Study, it was discovered that tax systems tend to be progressive but government expenditure seems to be a more effective tool for income redistribution. In his work, titled, “an empirical investigation into the determinants of income distribution in the Nigeria manufacturing sector”, Oguntuase (as cited in Awe & Rufus, 2012) expressed the income distribution in the manufacturing sector (proxy by GINI coefficient) as a function of a number of explanatory variables such as: employment rate (EMP), inflationary rate (INFR), manufacturing sector share of the Nigerian GDP (MGDP), government expenditure on social services (GSEXP), and literacy rate (proxy for Education) LITR. Using the Co-integration and Error Correction Model (ECM), the empirical results of the study revealed that the level of education, manufacturing sector share of the GDP, government social expenditure and employment rate were true determinants of income distribution in the Nigeria manufacturing sector. The study further revealed that both manufacturing sector share of the GDP and employment rate exhibited an inverse relationship with the Gini coefficient of income distribution in the Nigerian manufacturing sector, while both government social expenditure and literacy rate (proxy for education) had a direct relationship with the Gini coefficient of income distribution in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. Mallaye, Yogo and Timba (2015) examined the empirical effects of oil rent on income inequality using data on a sample of 40 developing countries. Employing a dynamic panel data specification over the period 1996-2008, the econometric results yielded two important findings. First, it was discovered that there exist a non-linear (U-shaped) relationship between oil rent and inequality. Thus, oil rent lowers inequality in the short-run. This effect then diminishes over time as the oil revenues increase. The result further showed that the fall in income inequality as a result of the increase in the oil rent is fully absorbed by the increase in corruption.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

A prominent theory usually associated with natural resources and income inequality is the Resource curse theory, also known as the Dutch disease. This theory had its origin from the Netherlands. Following the discovery of natural gas in the North Sea in the 1970s, the Dutch found that their manufacturing sector (pre-existing domestic sector) suddenly started performing more poorly than expected. The Resource curse broadly refers to the idea that countries with greater natural resource wealth grow slower than countries that are poor in natural resources (Martin & Crookes, 2013). Thus, the main idea surrounding the resource curse theory is that a sudden rise in the value of natural resource (oil revenue) exports results in an increase in the real exchange rate, promote an adverse balance of payments on the cost of imported goods when prices fall, boost wages for skilled labour and reduce the incentive to risk investment in non-oil sectors (Schubert, as cited in Mallaye et al., 2015).

However, a shift from the pre-existing domestic sector to the oil sector can have adverse effects on the economy through several channels. One of such channels is through income distribution. For instance, if returns to export sectors such as manufacturing or agriculture are more equitably distributed than the returns from the natural resource (oil) sector, then such sectoral shift can lead to a rise in income inequality. Martin and Crookes (2013) further asserted that inspite of natural

resource abundance (crude oil), Nigeria is yet to experience sustainable economic growth. Gylfason (as cited in Moradi, 2009) concludes that as the natural resource sector expands relative to other sectors, the returns to human capital decrease likewise investment in education, thus leading to less development.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data and Data Source

Annual time series data were collected from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, Index Mundi, World Bank Indicators, Bakare (2012), and Ilaboya and Ohonba (2013). The study spanned a period of 25 years, ranging from 1990-2014.

3.2 Model Specification

The model of the study was a modification of the models of Moradi (2009), and Awe and Rufus (2012). Moradi (2009) studied “oil resource abundance, economic growth and income distribution in Iran” using the model:

$$GINI_t = y_0 + y_1 Y_t + y_2 E_t + y_3 OR_t + \delta D_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

GINI is the Gini coefficient as a proxy for income distribution;

E is the average years of school attainment for the population aged 15 and over;

Y is the level of the GDP per capita;

OR represents per capital real oil revenue;

D is a set of dummy variables.

Awe and Rufus (2012) examined the determinants of income distribution in the Nigerian Economy (1977-2005) using the model:

$$GINIC = f(EMPR, INFR, GDP, HE, EDE)_t$$

$$GINIC_t = a_0 + a_1 EMPR_t + a_2 INFR_t + a_3 GDP_t + a_4 HE_t + a_5 EDE_t + U_t$$

Where:

GINIC_t = Gini coefficient of income distribution in the Nigeria economy.

EMPR_t = Employment rate in the Nigerian economy.

GDP_t = Growth rate of output in the Nigerian economy.

HE_t = Government expenditure on health in the Nigerian economy proxy by recurrent expenditure on health.

EDE_t = Government expenditure on Education in the Nigerian economy proxy by recurrent expenditure on education.

U_t = Stochastic variables.

a_0 = Intercept of the relationship.

$a_1 - a_5$ = Slope coefficients.

Both models above were modified to suit the country-specific nature of this study and in order to ascertain the effect of oil revenue and other variables on income inequality in Nigeria, the model for this study is specified thus:

$$GINI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OIL\ REV + \beta_2 INFL + \beta_3 RGDP + \beta_4 GREXP + \varepsilon$$

Where:

GINI = Gini coefficient from 1990-2013;

OIL REV = Oil revenue in the Nigerian economy;

INFL = Inflation rate in the Nigerian economy;

RGDP = Real GDP in the Nigerian economy;

GREXP = Government recurrent expenditure on social and community services;

ε = Error term;

β_0 = Intercept of the relationship; and

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Unknown coefficients of the variables.

3.3 Apriori Expectation

RealGDP and Government recurrent expenditures on social and community services (GREXP) are expected to have a positive relationship with Gini coefficient (GINI); a proxy for income distribution. Also, Oil revenue (OIL REV) and inflation rate (INFL) are expected to have an inverse relationship with Gini coefficient.

3.4 Data Estimation Technique

The study employed the Error Correction Model (ECM).

4.0 ESTIMATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study utilized time series data obtained from published journals and the Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Statistical Bulletin. The study covered a period of 25 years, ranging from 1990-

2014. The preliminary test was first carried out using the ADF Test to ascertain if there exist a level of stationarity among estimating parameters. The Error Correction Model (ECM) was employed to ascertain if any form of long run relationship exist among the variables.

4.1 UNIT ROOT TEST

@ SECOND DIFFERENCE

VARIABLE	ADF	CRITICAL VALUE	P- VALUE	REMARK
GINI	-5.137275	-3.658446	0.0028	Stationary
INFL	-7.609205	-3.632896	0.0000	Stationary
OIL REV	-3.770880	-3.673616	0.0419	Stationary
RGDP	-3.920442	-3.673616	0.0318	Stationary
GREXP	-5.757146	-3.632896	0.0006	Stationary

Source: *Author's Computation (2015)*

From the result of the Unit Root test carried out on each of the variables in the model to ascertain their level of stationality, all the variables were found to be stationary at second difference. This therefore gives an indicative premise that there is the existence of a unit root in the model.

4.2 PARSIMONIOUS ERROR CORRECTION MODEL:

Dependent Variable: D(GINI)

Method: Least Squares

Sample (adjusted): 1991 2014

Included observations: 24 after adjustments

HAC standard errors & covariance (Bartlett kernel, Newey-West fixed bandwidth = 3.0000)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GREXP)	-3.78E-06	6.48E-05	-0.058335	0.9541
D(INFL)	-0.001065	0.000586	-1.818855	0.0856
D(OIL REV)	-1.20E-06	4.76E-06	-0.252134	0.8038
D(RGDP)	5.92E-07	2.69E-07	2.198320	0.0412
ECM(-1)	-0.973254	0.301790	-3.224937	0.0047
C	-0.003716	0.008910	-0.417101	0.6815
R-squared	0.527643	Mean dependent var		-0.004167
Adjusted R-squared	0.396433	S.D. dependent var		0.053139
S.E. of regression	0.041283	Akaike info criterion		-3.324407
Sum squared resid	0.030677	Schwarz criterion		-3.029894
Log likelihood	45.89288	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.246272
F-statistic	4.021359	Durbin-Watson stat		1.874928
Prob(F-statistic)	0.012613	Wald F-statistic		5.469186
Prob(Wald F-statistic)	0.003114			

Source: *Eviews 8.0*

From the table above, an examination of the coefficient of determination depicted as R^2 shows that about 53% of the systematic variation in Gini coefficient, a proxy for income inequality was caused by the regressors in the model. While the balance (47%) was captured by the error term, though unexplained by the model. However, the overall model was found to be statistically significant with a calculated F-statistic value of 4.02 and associate probability value which was less than the critical F-value at 5% level of significance. Hence, there exists a joint significant effect of the explanatory variables on income inequality in Nigeria over the period under study.

The above result revealed that in the short-run, D(INFL) had statistically a significant negative impact on income inequality in Nigeria, having reported t-statistics of (-1.818855) with negative coefficient of (-0.001065) at 5% level of significance. D(OIL REV) and D(GSEXP) were found to have a negative impact on income inequality in Nigeria, though their impact was statistically negligible (-0.252134) and (-0.058335) respectively at 5% level of significance. However, the variable D(RGDP) was found to have a statistically positive significant relationship with income inequality in Nigeria having reported a positive t-statistic value of (2.198320). The Durbin-Watson statistics of (1.87) was substantially close to two, thus indicating the absence of autocorrelation.

In line with expectation, Oil revenue was found to exert a negative statistically insignificant impact on income inequality in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings of Moradi (2009), and Mallaye et al., (2015) who found a negative (not very strong) relationship between oil revenue and income inequality, but it is at variance with the findings of Martin and Crookes (2013) who found higher oil prices to have increased inequality. Inflation rate exhibited a robust negative relationship with income inequality. This finding is in tandem with the findings of Rossana and Hoeven (2001) who revealed that in high inflation countries, restrictive monetary policy often reduces income inequality, but it's at divergence with the findings of Jose and Teilings (2002); and Awe and Rufus (2012) who found inflation to increase income inequality. RGDP was also found to exhibit a robust positive relationship with income inequality in Nigeria. This finding is inconsistent with the findings of Jose and Teilings (2002); Oguntuase, (2007); Awe and Rufus, (2012); Giovanni, (2012); & Ilaboya and Ohonba, (2013) who found GDP to reduce income inequality.

Government recurrent expenditure on social and community services was found to be negatively related with income inequality. This finding is at variance with the findings of Oguntuase (2007) who found government social expenditure to increase income inequality. However, this finding corroborates with the findings of Jose and Teilings (2002); and Irish et al., (2012) who found government social expenditure to reduce income inequality.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATION

5.1 Conclusion

The central objective of this study was to determine the impact of oil revenue on income inequality in Nigeria against the backdrop of the huge gap between the poor and the rich in the Nigerian economy. Oil revenue since its discovery in Nigeria has been a very huge contributor to

the nation's total earnings annually. From the research findings above, oil revenue was found to reduce income inequality in Nigeria. However, this fall in income inequality as a result of increase in oil revenue is swallowed up by high level of corruption in the oil industry. This study, therefore advances the following recommendations.

5.2 Policy Implication

1. Though oil revenue, from the result of the empirical analysis reduces income inequality in Nigeria, in reality, the opposite is the case. This is due to the high level of corruption in the oil industry. Therefore, government should put measures in place in order to checkmate the high level of corruption in the oil industry.
2. The result of the findings also revealed that RealGDP had a robust positive relationship with income inequality. Therefore, government should put measures in place towards the improvement RealGDP especially in the informal sector of the economy in order to reduce the wide gap between the poor and the rich in the country.
3. Since from findings, government recurrent expenditure on social and community services reduces income inequality, government should ensure its sustenance by continuous provision of social amenities to the people which will lead to more development in the economy.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: TEST FOR STATIONARITY OF THE RESIDUALS AT LEVELS

Null Hypothesis: ECM has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend

Lag Length: 2 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=5)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.255461	0.0146
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.440739	
5% level	-3.632896	
10% level	-3.254671	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

APPENDIX 2: TEST FOR STATIONARITY OF GREXP @ 2nd difference

Null Hypothesis: D(GREXP,2) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.757146	0.0006
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.440739	
5% level	-3.632896	
10% level	-3.254671	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

APPENDIX 3: TEST FOR STATIONARITY OF GINI @ 2nd difference

Null Hypothesis: D(GINI,2) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend

Lag Length: 2 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.137275	0.0028
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.498307	
5% level	-3.658446	
10% level	-3.268973	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

APPENDIX 4: TEST FOR STATIONARITY OF INFL @ 2nd difference

Null Hypothesis: D(INFL,2) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-7.609205	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.440739	
5% level	-3.632896	
10% level	-3.254671	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

APPENDIX 5: TEST FOR STATIONARITY OF OIL REV @ 2nd difference

Null Hypothesis: D(OIL REV,2) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 3 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.770880	0.0419
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.532598	
5% level	-3.673616	
10% level	-3.277364	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

APPENDIX 6: TEST FOR STATIONARITY OF RGDP @ 2nd difference

Null Hypothesis: D(RGDP,2) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 3 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.920442	0.0318
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.532598	
5% level	-3.673616	
10% level	-3.277364	